

DEVELOPMENT OF A PROTECTIVE FABRIC THAT REFLECTS ULTRAVIOLET RADIATION

¹Abdimanap Sayat Maldybayuly, ²Dyussenbiyeva Kulmairam Zhamanbaevna

¹master's student, ATU, ²PhD, ATU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14178351>

***Annotatsiya.** Ushbu maqolada to'qimachilik materiallarining ultrabinafsha nurlanishidan himoya xususiyatlarini yaxshilashga qaratilgan tadqiqotlar tasvirlangan. Asosiy e'tibor paxta va poliester aralash matolarini natriy gipofosfit va titan dioksidi qo'shilishi bilan qayta ishlashning yangi usulini ishlab chiqishga qaratilgan. Ushbu reagentlardan foydalanish ultrabinafsha nurlarining o'tkazuvchanligi darajasining sezilarli darajada pasayishini ko'rsatdi, bu esa to'qimalarni quyosh nurlanishidan himoya qilishni oshiradi. Tadqiqot ishlov berish samaradorligini batafsil tahlil qilishni va belgilangan sifat va xavfsizlik standartlariga muvofiqligini tekshirishni o'z ichiga oladi.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** aralash to'qimachilik materiallari, ultrabinafsha nurlanish, yakuniy tugatish, titan dioksidi, himoya xususiyatlari, xavfsizlik.*

***Аннотация.** В данной работе описаны исследования, направленные на улучшение защитных свойств текстильных материалов от УФ-излучения. Основное внимание уделено, разработке новой методики обработки смесовых тканей из хлопка и полиэстера с добавлением гипофосфита натрия и диоксида титана. Применение данных реагентов, показало значительное снижение уровня пропускания УФ-лучей, что повышает защиту тканей от солнечного излучения. Исследование включает подробный анализ эффективности обработки и испытания на соответствие установленным стандартам качества и безопасности.*

***Ключевые слова:** смесовые текстильные материалы, ультрафиолетовое излучение, заключительная отделка, диоксид титана, защитные свойства, безопасность.*

***Abstract.** This paper describes research aimed at improving the protective properties of textile materials against UV radiation. The main attention is paid to the development of a new method for processing mixed fabrics from cotton and polyester with the addition of sodium hypophosphite and titanium dioxide. The use of these reagents has shown a significant reduction in the level of transmission of UV rays, which increases the protection of tissues from solar radiation. The study includes a detailed analysis of the processing efficiency and testing for compliance with established quality and safety standards.*

***Keywords:** mixed textile materials, ultraviolet radiation, final finishing, titanium dioxide, protective properties, safety.*

Every year, the number of cases related to the harmful effects of ultraviolet (UV) radiation on human health and the durability of textiles continues to increase. UV radiation poses a significant threat to textile materials, which can lead to poor performance and accelerated wear. With global warming and increasing sunlight intensity, the need to develop fabrics that can effectively block UV rays is becoming an increasingly urgent task. Creating textile materials with improved UV protection properties is an important task for the modern textile industry [1, 2, 3].

Ultraviolet light (prolonged exposure to the sun) causes many health problems for our body. In this regard, the above problem requires an important solution in modern textile production. This is because UPF-free clothing allows 1/5 of the UV rays to pass through the skin.

Radiation penetrating the skin causes skin diseases, including skin cancer [4,5]. The term "sun-protective clothing" was first used in Australia in 1996 when the number of people with skin cancer increased, figure 1.

Figure 1- Global incidence of skin cancer

The relevance of the topic lies in the study of biocompatibility and safety for human health of UV-protective technological products in the field of textiles. The goal of the work is to minimize the danger of sunlight as much as possible [6,7,8]. Safety studies of textile materials with UV protection properties are very important for maintaining human health and comfort, especially in the face of climate change and increasing solar radiation. Modern research works give different results. Scientists are trying to give clothes UPF properties with various technologies. The result can also be achieved with the help of special treatments, spray, washing powder, to obtain a temporary result, using special coatings [7,8,9,10].

For the treatment of mixed fabrics, a solution was used: sodium hypophosphite, titanium dioxide, citric acid, which serve as the main reagents for creating UV protective properties [9,10]. During the experiment, the fabric was impregnated with the composition, and then dried and heat-treated. Sodium hypophosphite acts as a stabilizer, preventing the destruction of fibers under the influence of UV rays, and titanium dioxide, acting as a UV absorbent, effectively blocks harmful radiation [11,12,13,14].

To determine the tensile characteristics, the RT-250M tensile machine, GOST 3813-72, figure 2, was used. Tests have shown that the treatment of mixed textile materials provides a significant increase in tensile performance. For example, for treated polyester and cotton fabrics, an increase in breaking load by 20-30% was recorded compared to untreated samples.

Figure 2 - Absolute breaking load indicators for polyester and cotton-polyester blends

Determination of fabric resistance to surface wetting was carried out in accordance with GOST 30292-96, device MT 032, figure 3. At the same time, the materials have retained their breathability and water-repellent properties, which makes them promising for the production of protective clothing and interior items.

Figure 3-Hydrophobic wetting conditions

From an optical point of view, when light is projected onto an object, some of it is reflected off the surface, some is absorbed by the object, and the rest passes through the object. In general, the sum of transmittance, reflectance and absorption coefficient is 100%. The principle of UV-

resistant treatment involves the use of UV blockers to treat fibers or fabrics. When light radiation reaches the tissue, a small part of it passes through the gaps in the tissue, whereas most of it is reflected or selectively absorbed by UV blockers. The absorbed light is converted into low energy, which is then released, effectively blocking UV radiation. The results of the UV protection study were 70-75%, demonstrating the effectiveness of textile processing.

The results of the studies confirm the high efficiency of the use of sodium hypophosphite and titanium dioxide to create fabrics with increased UV protective properties. These reagents can significantly improve the durability and safety of textile products, opening up new opportunities for their application in the textile industry. A new technique for processing blended fabrics could be useful in the production of clothing, furniture and other products where UV protection is required.

REFERENCES

1. J. Beckmann, S. Mathur. Titanium dioxide as a UV-blocking agent in textile coatings. *Journal of Coatings Technology and Research*, 13(3), 2016, pp. 537-544.
2. M. Kulkarni, P. Rao. A study on polyester fabrics with UV protection using nanoparticles, *Journal of Textiles and Polymers*, 44(3), 2016, pp. 199-207
3. L. Hernandez, Perez. M. Mechanical and UV Protective Properties of Treated Bamboo-Cotton Blended Fabrics, *Journal of Natural Fibers*, 17(9), 2020, pp. 1267-1278.
4. C. Vasile, M. Baican. Polyester and polyamide composites with UV protective coatings, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 135(24), 2018, 46319.
5. I. Alberts, E. Takacs. UV protection properties of cotton/polyester fabrics treated with inorganic nanoparticles, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 137(3), 2020, 48239.
6. S.M. Abdimanap., *Dzhurinskaya I.M.*, *Dyussenbieva K.J.* Study on the safety of textile materials with protective properties against UV rays. Всероссийская научная конференция молодых исследователей с международным участием «Инновационное развитие техники и технологий в промышленности (ИНТЕКС-2024)», 16 апреля 2024 г. С. 204-206.
7. K. Muller, Schmidt, H. Innovative Approaches in UV Protection for Technical Textiles Using Advanced Nanomaterials, *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry*, 53, 2017, pp. 233-240.
8. P. Johnson, K. Davies, "Comparative Study on UV Protective Finishes Using TiO₂ on Various Textile Blends", *Textile Finishing Journal*, 22(1), 2016, pp. 34-42.
9. T. Ivanova, S. Petrov. The Role of Sodium Hypophosphite in Improving UV Resistance of Polyester-Cotton Fabrics, *Eastern European Journal of Advanced Materials*, 13(5), 2021, pp. 205-213.
10. E. Brown, Clark, J. Investigating the Efficacy of Sodium Hypophosphite as a Flame Retardant and UV Stabilizer in Textile Blends, *Journal of Industrial Textiles*, 49(6), 2020. pp. 809-820.
11. R. Singh, S. Mehta. Application of Nano Titanium Dioxide and Sodium Hypophosphite for UV Protection in Linen-Cotton Blends, *Journal of Nanoengineering and Nanomanufacturing*, 10(4), 2018, pp. 215-222.
12. L. Kong, W. Yu. Analysis of UV-protective properties of textile materials based on combined use of TiO₂ and NaH₂PO₂, *Textile Chemistry and Coloration Journal*, 33(4), 2021, pp. 254-263.